

20M1259 REPORT
A Reflective Critique Report
BM-5102 Organisational Behavior

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Before experience

The year 2020 brought forth various challenges. As a background, I graduated last year, 22 August 2019, with a bachelor's degree in *Geology*. After graduation, I immediately started looking for a job. However, I discovered that my degree in *Geology* was not a popular choice for companies to take, as there were limited options in jobs that I could relate to, in terms of knowledge and skills that are more fitting to the petroleum industry. While waiting for a permanent job, I took part-time work to gain the experience that many organizations sought for, but the outbreak of COVID-19 only increased the difficulty of finding a job. With that, I decided to enroll back into University to pursue my Masters Degree. In Brunei, our government, especially the Ministry of Health, handled the pandemic well. Cases started decreasing and schools eventually reopened. However, preventive measures were still in place, so students were told to stay home and attend class virtually, which was applied to university students as well.

With reflection, the experience above highlighted the importance of planning and foresight. Hill (2019) detailed that progress is obtained by firstly reviewing the current situation and then identifying prospective opportunities for growth. As I lacked the skills that most employers were looking for, I intend to join various short-term programs that teach leadership and management to gain a first hand experience while simultaneously pursuing my masters. Currently, I am the operational manager for *BIBD Yes!*, an event that will be finished by 13th December 2020. I also intend to do job-seeking in parallel to my masters, so by the time I graduate, I will be equipped with the skills and actual experience that employers are looking for.

As mentioned before, because I came from a science background, entering into a business-oriented masters was a new experience. The decision of pursuing master's in management was due to extrinsic and intrinsic values in accordance with Herzberg's Motivator-Hygiene Theory, as cited by Ramlall (2004). According to his theory, "motivators" are factors that employees commonly link to satisfying experiences. These motivators are also intrinsic values in nature: achievement, recognition, the work itself, responsibility, advancement, and growth. "Hygiene" factors, on the other hand, refer to dissatisfying experiences, largely from extrinsic, non-job-related factors such as company policies, salary, co-worker relations and supervisory styles.

Hence, my main motivation is my desire for recognition and achievements. I realised that I had become stagnant and stopped growing as a person, due to the fact that job-hunting in Brunei is difficult. Because of this uncertainty, I am worried for my future. I hoped that, with a master's in management, I am able to gain a more marketable educational background and obtain skills that companies are seeking, which will increase my chances of getting a job in the future. My extrinsic motivator was, and still is, possessing a job that offers me stability and pays a salary that is appropriate to my qualifications. This is reaffirmed by Musa & Idris (2020) where they explained the young people in Brunei prioritise high income, job security and prestige because it has become a cultural norm and many believed it would lead to personal and career development and progression.

However, master's in management was not what I had expected it to be. I thought it would be bearable, but I have never thought I would dedicate most of my time including my leisure time to it. The overwhelming unfamiliar terms, the plethora of theories and the large amount of assignments to be completed within a tight schedule and in addition, the restriction of face-to-face interactions was taxing for me. Therefore, for this one semester, adapting to the

'new norm' has been quite difficult especially in terms of motivation to attend class and staying focused. Moreover, I believe, all the students had difficulty adjusting to the sudden huge amount of workload due to the whole semester being based on 100% coursework. This was clearly apparent in one of my modules, Organisational Behaviour, which tested my time management skills and initiative to self-study.

For this module, we were given two big assignments which are individual analysis and case study reports. This paper will be an analysis of my experience with both assignments.

During experience

For my individual analysis report, the first subject(s) I initially wanted to research about was motivation and rate of turnover of Generation Y. The reason behind it was because it was the current problem faced in Brunei and other countries where *Generation Y* or *millennials* are known to be the generation that 'job-hops' from one job to another, never loyal to a company for long. I believed that the reason behind the unloyalty was job satisfaction which linked to motivation where *Generation Y* would feel more motivated and satisfied with their current position when their needs are met by the organization. I wanted to prove that *Generation Y* can actually be committed but because they were born in an era far different than their predecessors, their needs are just different and it may be beneficial for an organization to understand, so they can strategize ways to accommodate the generational differences. However, during the first class with Dr Rozie, our lecturer for Organisational Behaviour, I discovered many of my peers were already planning to write on motivation and rate of turnover. I desired to be different but still related to my first motive.

The topic I had finally decided upon was intrinsic work values and organizational commitment of Generation Y. It still had a relation with the first topic, I chose but my main interest was to reveal that Generation Y mostly do prioritise intrinsic work values but due to their current stage in their career, many are working to live, attributing extrinsic work values. Moreover, there was a lack of literature that displayed those kinds of findings. In terms of research questions, from the literature I read, I found that there were many factors that could affect organizational commitment of Generation Y and it was not only related to work values.

The process I had difficulties in was outlining my research, especially the aspect of getting access to companies who would consent to participate in my research. I knew it was going to be difficult for me to get the companies to willingly participate in my research as many are wary of what could be shared by their employees. Moreover, my methodology consisted of a survey and semi-structured interview so I needed a large number of *Generation Y* respondents so I could generalize my research. Usually companies with that kind of amount are under the public sector, and that could be a long process especially without knowing a gatekeeper. I realized how important it was to have networks. Cole (2019) wrote that networking brings forth various benefits, among them is that it makes job-seekers more noticeable to employers, reassures employers of the job-seeker's abilities and provides new opportunities for self development as well as job prospects that may not have been available to anyone. To achieve this, I will be attending a networking dinner on 13th December 2020 under the *BIBD Yes!* event.

After the outline submission, we had assignments pertaining to the components of the research, such as a 'skeleton' of our research and literature view. According to Dr Rozie, the

reasoning behind our given tasks is to facilitate our workflow towards our final submission; to prevent last minute preparatory work which I have to agree, it did indeed help me plan ahead and see how I want my research to flow, what aspects I needed to consider and what approach I needed to utilize in order to reach the objectives of my research. If we were to look this in an organization point of view, planning ahead is a crucial method all companies must practice because it contributes the performance success such as in terms of improved focus and flexibility where an organisation that is both willing and flexible to change and adapt to the shifting circumstances without losing focus, will operate with an orientation towards the future rather than the past. Therefore, an individual who is flexible in adjusting their career paths to fit something new and develop opportunities will be more successful than the individual who remains stagnant (Schermerhorn, 2013).

Moreover, along the journey to complete my research, Dr Rozie has done the best she could to guide us, to mould us into the best version of ourselves. Her methods were different – stricter and less spoon-feeding – but it forced her students to be independent, a useful skill needed when working.

However, there were a lot of hurdles that I had to get through in order to complete the research. Firstly, was deciding the size and type of samples. Among the questions that I thought about was how to narrow the research down, who are my respondents, from what industry and how many respondents are considered adequate. My indecisiveness and over-thinking were the problems that I faced when I was contacting every company possible regardless of the type of industry, just so I could obtain participants to do my research. I did not have an aim at the time, and it was already September, so a sense of urgency grew day by day. I was behind schedule, and I needed approval from the HR office specifically the ethics division. Eventually, I based my research on the educational sectors specifically tuition centres and immediately started reaching out to the tuition centres in Brunei through friends and families. This highlighted how I lack in decision making and also, my carelessness of not taking into account the small variables that were my main focus of the research and may resulted in me to do things last minute. In my opinion, this stems from my lack of self-confidence which is further supported by Schermerhorn (2013) where he explained that managers require self-confidence to make decisions and carry out the implementation of these decisions.

However, complications appeared when Dr Rozie announced there was a change in procedures concerning attainment of approval from the division of ethics especially in terms of the ethical forms. The office announced that they will no longer accept any more request forms due to the overwhelming amount. *Systematic Literature Review* was the solution suggested by Dr Rozie, for the students that have yet to receive their approval and this applied to both the individual analysis and group case study report.

The change in objectives made me disoriented, as what I initially wanted to prove was whether there was a case where the findings were false, especially in the bruneian context. Due to circumstances, this was not possible to prove, so I was disappointed that I could not explore the ideas more freely. Nevertheless, one needs to be able to adapt to any given situation and that is exactly what I chose to do. I rewrote the skeleton of my report and started looking for articles, then I categorised them according to country, type of industry and aim of the research done. To be honest, the experience was extremely overwhelming for me. The preparations for the systematic literature review were inadequate; there was only one month left until final submission, but more time was required to prepare various aspects of the research such as reading for the literature review while also balancing out pending assignments.

The feeling of being overwhelmed increased tenfold when I took a part-time job as an operation manager for a company. The weight of my responsibilities from my new position and the pending assignments – that were mostly group work – were challenging my time management skills and patience. Due to this, I was losing sleep trying to complete all my responsibilities. On the daily, I would try to focus on my job while also checking up on the progress of my teammates and participating in discussion to the best of my abilities and once everything was settled, I would attend to my group projects first. I would complete the tasks that were assigned to me then move on to urgent matters concerning my job if there was any. The experience gave me the exposure to hone my time management skills while also giving me the experience to choose which task I should give priority first.

During one of the groupworks, I struggled to manage my time due to the complications with some members of my team who either did not do work or did their work very inefficiently. As I did not want to have bad grades, I contacted them first and let them know the mistakes as to why it was the wrong way to do it. However, when they did not deliver properly, I had to reassess their work, which affected my scheduling. The circumstances forced me to also do my report at the last minute. Yet, I have no one to blame but myself, since it highlights the need to not to over-rely on friends. Having personal relations with people, sometimes it is ironically harder to correct their ways as the work can become personal, and any animosity can affect the relationship outside of work. In other words, it is better to be in the same team as individuals with good rapport and are cooperative.

To be critical, the outcome individual analysis report was personally a dissatisfying report. It did not reflect my skills and it lacks the quality I expected all my assignments to have. I believe I could have written a better report.

In terms of the group case study, our main objective of the study was to investigate the team performance of pilots from Royal Brunei specifically in terms of their morale, motivation, and commitment. For the research, we decided to do a mixed method approach where we opted for a structured interview with open-end questions and self-developed survey. However, with the change of ethical regulations, our leader consulted with Dr Rozie to search for an alternative way to do the research without having to write a systematic review and was suggested an option to do a focus group.

The focus group was then divided into two groups but there were a total of 8 pilots. However, due to personal reasons I was unable to attend both interviews so for the first interview it was done solely by our leader and the second interview, she was accompanied by the other team members. To make up with my absence, I volunteered to transcribe the first interview on my own and it was actually my first time doing it. It was a great and enjoyable experience because it was interesting to listen to the conversation and understand the situation from their perspective which usually is not shared publicly. After transcribing, the delegation of each section of the report was divided fairly.

Moreover, our leader displayed great leadership, from the beginning she assigned us our roles, the goals we need to achieve and the standard of quality she expected. She exuded transactional and transformational skills needed in a leader. Transactional skills are defined as the skills needed to enable daily operation of the team, while transformational skills are skills that enable the team to work together while also encouraging innovative approaches (Bass, 1990 as cited by Outhwaite, 2003).

Overall, my group and I were satisfied with the outcome of the case study as we were able to investigate the pilots' morale, commitment, and team performance towards Royal Brunei even though we did not collect information that was initially planned. The chemistry of the group was amazing, we had great teamwork and there were no disagreements, everyone had the same goals in mind. Furthermore, I built a great relationship with our leader in terms of friendship since we were initially strangers before masters and learnt that we have the same work ethics as we were each other's support in this assignment.

However, my team and I also felt pressured in completing the report as we were on a tight schedule; there were two other reports that had to be submitted on the same day. We had to plan to complete this group case study first before proceeding with the other modules' assignments but due to unforeseen circumstances, we had to balance all three assignments and actively participate in group meetings for the other modules.

Completion of Experience

Throughout my experience, I realised that it is important to have good rapport with my team members, especially if they share the same work ethics. Mary's organisation as a community, as cited by Caramela (2018), highlighted the need of having a flow of communication where team members are able to talk freely and resolve issues without animosity.

The experience of masters also gave me an opportunity to network and create new relationships that were beyond my expectations. From the various groupworks, I was able to befriend my fellow colleagues who had amazing work ethics and I inspire to attain their level of organisation and leadership.

I believe that the experience of masters also taught me how to manage between academia and my part-time job. It was imperative for me to learn how to compartmentalise and assign time between my coursework and my part-time tasks, else I would only achieve to overwhelm myself, as I learned in the beginning of the semester since taking the job.

Lastly, throughout all the modules that I have taken during this semester of Masters, all of the modules highlighted the need to believe in ourselves, develop and have patience, while also emphasising the need to trust in one's abilities. In other words, Masters have facilitated my growth to become a better individual, when compared to when I first started out.

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